

MODERN PEDAGOGICAL METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *Today, the education system cannot be imagined without modern methods and technologies. This article discusses the appearance, essence, efficiency and technology of these methods.*

Keywords: *English language, method, technology, education, teaching.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, there are many methods for learning a foreign language in higher education institutions. Each method has certain characteristics, some are more popular and in demand, some are less popular. This article will discuss the basic methods for students to learn English.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modern methods of teaching English in higher education institutions

In the modern world, English is very popular; moreover, this language is the language of international communication and is known all over the world. Today there are a huge variety of methods for teaching English. In addition, new ones are regularly developed, so now each teacher can choose the optimal working method for himself.

Currently, when teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions, classical methods are most often used. Namely:

- 1. Direct method.*
- 2. Grammar-translation method of teaching.*
- 3. Audiovisual and audiolingual methods.*
- 4. Communicative method.*

In this article we will look at each of these techniques in more detail.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Direct method of teaching a foreign language

The essence of this technique is that the teacher pays more attention to studying the spoken language itself, which is used in everyday life. The developers of this method considered that the intermediary language, that is, the language in which teaching is conducted, inhibits the learning of a foreign language. Thus, students are artificially introduced into the world of the language they are learning.

The entire lesson is conducted in English; the teacher must also give explanations and new topics in English. Only English-language literature is used.

When teaching English using this method, the role of the teacher in the successful acquisition of knowledge by students is key. That is, his speech must be absolutely clear and correct, his pronunciation must be perfect, since the students will constantly repeat exactly after the teacher. The ideal option for a direct teaching method would be to have a native English speaker as a teacher [4].

Grammar-translation method

The grammar-translation method is the main one in the modern education system. This is a classic method that has been used for decades. Its prevalence is also due to the fact that most teachers themselves trained using this method.

The goal of the grammar-translation method is to learn to read and translate using grammatical rules.

The disadvantages of this method include the fact that insufficient attention is paid to the lexical part. Learning vocabulary comes down to rote learning of words. Reading and translation are performed in a strict manner. In addition, the texts offered for reading usually relate to complex fiction, therefore, the student studies only the literary language. Once in a linguistic environment, it will be very difficult for him to understand those around him, even with a good knowledge of the literary language.

Audiovisual and audiolingual methods

The essence of both methods is to transfer the language through clear structures; learning occurs using audio and video recordings.

The audiovisual teaching method involves illustrating speech with appropriate pictures, that is, students are shown videos, feature films and documentaries in English. In this case, students have two channels of perception working simultaneously - visual and auditory, as a result of which associations arise in the students' heads, which allows them to better memorize the language. The goal of the methods is to master a living, spoken language [1].

Communicative method

Currently, an increasing number of teachers are turning to the communicative method of learning English. The object of this method is speech itself, that is, this technique primarily teaches how to communicate.

The communicative method implies greater student activity. The teacher's task in this case will be to involve everyone in the audience in the conversation. For better memorization and use of the language, it is necessary to load all channels of perception.

The essence of the communicative method is to create real communication situations. When recreating the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. A very important advantage of the communicative method is that it has a huge variety of exercises: role-playing games, dialogues, simulation of real communication are used here [2].

CONCLUSION

At first, the communicative method was rejected, but now it again occupies a leading position along with the traditional grammatical-translation method. Most teachers at modern universities prefer these two methods, and they are often used in combination. The direct method is used extremely rarely in higher educational institutions, partly due to the lack of real native speakers among teachers, and partly due to the fact that the level of training of students after school is too low.

Audiovisual and audiolingual methods are not used in their pure form at all, but many teachers of universities and institutes from time to time conduct classes based on such methods. This allows you to diversify the general education program and interest students.

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